

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Oxidation of imidacloprid insecticide through PMS activation using CuFe₂O₄ nanoparticles: role of process parameters and surface modifications

Yeison Núñez-de la Rosa^{1,2}, Yoisel B. Broteron¹, Vladimir A. Ballesteros-Ballesteros²,
Luis Guillermo Cuadrado Durango¹, Jorge Luis Nisperuza Toledo², Moacir Rossi
Forim¹, Fernanda Lourdes de Souza³, Peter Hammer⁴, and José M. Aquino^{1,*}

¹Federal University of São Carlos (UFSCar), Department of Chemistry, 13565-905, São
Carlos – SP, Brazil

²Fundación Universitaria Los Libertadores, Faculty of Engineering and Basic Sciences,
111221, Bogotá, Colombia

³São Paulo University, Institute of Chemistry of São Carlos, Department of Chemistry
and Molecular Physics, Trabalhador São-Carlense Avenue, 400- CEP 13566-590, São
Carlos, SP, Brazil

⁴São Paulo State University (UNESP), Institute of Chemistry, Department of Physical
Chemistry, 14800-900, Araraquara – SP, Brazil

* Corresponding Author. Phone: + 55 16 3351 8727

E-mail address: *jmaquino@ufscar.br* (José M. Aquino)

Abbreviations

- AsP - As-prepared samples without *in situ* chemical activation using an oxidizer
- Cpt 400 – CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the co-precipitation method and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h
- Cpt 700 – CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the co-precipitation method and thermally treated at 700 °C for 1 h
- CuMF: copper magnetic ferrite
- DMPO - 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline *N*-oxide
- EI - Electrochemical impedance
- FTIR – Fourier transform infrared
- HRTEM – high-resolution transmission electron microscopy
- HO• – hydroxyl radical
- HPLC – high-performance liquid chromatography
- ICP-OES – Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectrometry
- IMD – Imidacloprid insecticide
- IMD fraction – $100 \times [\text{IMD}]_t / [\text{IMD}]_0$: [IMD] concentration at a specific time (*t*) and *t* = 0
- MS/MS – tandem mass spectrometry
- ¹O₂ – singlet oxygen
- PMS – peroxymonosulfate
- SO₄•⁻ – sulfate radical
- SG 400 – magnetic CuFe₂O₄ ferrite prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h
- SG 700 – CuFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally treated at 700 °C for 1 h
- UHPLC-QToF MS - ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time-of-flight mass analyzer
- Us – Assayed samples for the *in situ* chemical activation of PMS to oxidize IMD
- XRD – X-ray diffraction
- XPS – X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

Fig. S1 Chemical structure of imidacloprid (IMD) insecticide - $C_9H_{10}ClN_5O_2$ and MW: $255.662 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$.

Table S1 Instrumental parameters optimized during ICP-OES analyses.

Instrumental Parameters	Values
Integration time for the emission line (s)	5
Sample flow rate (mL min ⁻¹)	4.2
Sample flow rate during analysis (mL min ⁻¹)	2.1
Peristaltic pump stabilization time (s)	25
Applied radio frequency power (W)	1200
Auxiliary gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.25
Nebulizing gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	0.83
Cooling gas flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	16
Co emission line used (nm) and signal observation	228.616 (Axial)
Fe emission line used (nm) and signal observation	259.940 (Axial)

The ion composition and some physicochemical characteristics of tap water and simulated can be observed below.

Table S2 Chemical composition of tap water

Parameters	Experimental values
pH	6.14 – 6.20 (21.6 °C)
Conductivity / mS cm ⁻¹	32 μS cm ⁻¹ (21.2 °C)
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)*	0.0
[Na ⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	1.85
[K ⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	2.96
[Mg ²⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	1.47
[Ca ²⁺] / mg L ⁻¹	2.61
[Br ⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	5.32
[Cl ⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	0.58
[F ⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	Traces (not quantified)
[SO ₄ ²⁻] / mg L ⁻¹	0.28

*Total organic carbon (TOC) measurement carried out as described in: C.H.M. Fernandes, B.F. Silva, J.M. Aquino, On the performance of distinct electrochemical and solar-based advanced oxidation processes to mineralize the insecticide imidacloprid, *Chemosphere*. 275 (2021) 130010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130010>.

Text S1

Simulated municipal wastewater (SMWW)

The composition of SMWW used as a model for a secondary effluent matrix was prepared according to the work of Sánchez-Montes et al. [12], as well as receipts described in Zhang *et al.* [13] and in APHA Standard Methods [14] with modifications. The following chemicals were used:

i) inorganics salts: NaHCO₃ (96 mg L⁻¹), MgSO₄ (60 mg L⁻¹), NaCl (580 mg L⁻¹), and K₂HPO₄ (7.0 mg L⁻¹), CaSO₄·2H₂O (60 mg L⁻¹) and (NH₄)₂SO₄ (23.6 mg L⁻¹), KCl (4 mg L⁻¹).

ii) organic matter: beef extract (1.8 mg L⁻¹), peptone (2.7 mg L⁻¹), humic acid (4.2 mg L⁻¹), sodium lignin sulfonate (2.4 mg L⁻¹), sodium lauryl sulphate (0.9 mg L⁻¹), tannic acid (4.2 mg L⁻¹) and acacia gum powder (4.7 mg L⁻¹).

Table S3 Physicochemical parameters of SMWW effluent

Parameters	Experimental values
pH	7.43 – 7.50 (21.6 °C)
Conductivity / mS cm ⁻¹	1,309 μS cm ⁻¹ (20.8 °C)
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)*	2.76 ±0.33

*Total organic carbon (TOC) measurement carried out as described in: C.H.M. Fernandes, B.F. Silva, J.M. Aquino, On the performance of distinct electrochemical and solar-based advanced oxidation processes to mineralize the insecticide imidacloprid, *Chemosphere*. 275 (2021) 130010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130010>.

Text S2

Chromatographic conditions and mass spectrometry analyses for elucidation of IMD oxidation byproducts

Samples at varying treating times were analyzed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity II Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatograph (UHPLC – from Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Chromatographic separation was performed using a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 column (50 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm, Agilent, USA). The mobile phase consisted of 0.1% formic acid solution (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B). The chromatographic gradient used was as follows: 0-2 min, 20% B; 2.1-2.5 min, from 20 to 50% B; 2.5-7.0 min, from 50%-90% B. Column oven and autosampler temperatures were both set to 25 °C. The mobile phase flow and injection volume were 0.40 mL·min⁻¹ and 0.20 μL, respectively.

Mass spectra were obtained using an Agilent 6545B Q-ToF MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an ESI Jet interface and operated in the positive ion mode using a capillary voltage that varied from 2.0 to 3.0 kV. Table S3 shows the parameter values used during MS experiments that were optimized for the IMD standard.

Table S4 Q-ToF MS parameter values

Parameter	Value
Desolvation gas flow rate	10 L min ⁻¹
Gas temperature	250 °C
Nebulizer pressure	30 psi
Sheath gas temperature	275 °C
Sheath gas flow rate	10 L min ⁻¹
Nozzle voltage	115 V
Fragmentor voltage	60 V
Skimmer voltage	30 V
Octopole RF peak voltage	250 V
Collision energy	2 to 5 V

Molecular ions were simultaneously obtained by the MS^E acquisition mode. Data were collected in a range of 50 to 600 Da, with a sweep rate of 3.0 spectrum s⁻¹ and processed by MassHunter Workstation Software, version B.08.00.

Text S3

The determination of short-chain carboxylic acids was carried out using HPLC. This involved the use of a Rezex™ ROA-H column (300 mm × 7.8 mm i.d., 8 μm particle size, from Phenomenex®) as the stationary phase and a solution of 2.5 mmol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ as the mobile phase, with a flow rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹. The identification of carboxylic acids was achieved by comparing their retention times with those of standards that had been previously analyzed. The volume injected, the detection wavelength, and the column temperature were set at 25 μL, 210 nm, and 23 °C respectively.

The analysis of inorganic ions was performed using HPLC with a conductivity detector (Shimadzu CDD-10A SP). For the determination of anions, a Shodex SI-52 4E column was used as the stationary phase at 45 °C, and a 3.6 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂CO₃ solution was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹. This analysis utilized a chemical suppressor system (Thermo Scientific™ ACRS 500) that pumped a regenerating solution of 3.6 mmol L⁻¹ H₂SO₄ at a rate of 0.8 mL min⁻¹. In terms of cation determination, a Shodex YS-50 column was used as the stationary phase at 40 °C, and a mixture of 4.0 mmol L⁻¹ oxalic acid and 6.0 mmol L⁻¹ tartaric acid solution was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹, without the use of the suppressor system.

Text S4

Chromatographic and mass spectrometry conditions for elucidation of DMPO oxidation byproducts

To determine the main oxidation byproducts resulting from DMPO oxidation by unknown radical species, UHPLC analyses were carried out using a Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 column (50 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm, Agilent, USA) as stationary phase. The mobile phase consisted of 0.1% formic acid solution (solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B). A gradient elution mode at 0.350 mL min⁻¹ was used to separate the main products according to the following sequence: 0-1 min, 5% B; 1-10 min, 95% B; 10-10.1 min, 95-5% B; and 10.5-13 min, 5% B. The injection volume, column, and autosampler temperatures were set to 1.0 μL and 35 °C, respectively. Identification of main byproducts through mass spectrometry was performed using an Agilent 6545B Q-ToF MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an ESI Jet interface, operated in positive ion mode using a capillary voltage of 2.0 kV. The desolvation gas flow and gas flow in the cone were 11 and 10 L min⁻¹, respectively. For the mass confirmation of the detected byproducts, the collision energies ranged from 5 V to 16 V. Other variables such as source temperature, fragmentation voltage, skimmer voltage, and nozzle voltage were set to 300 °C, 40 V, 35 V and 225 V, respectively. Molecular and fragment ions were simultaneously obtained by the MS^E acquisition mode. Data collected were analyzed ranging from 50 to 600 Da and processed by the MassHunter Workstation Software version B.08.00 (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA).

DMPO oxidation by unknown radical species were performed using 10 mL of deionized H₂O with pH adjusted to 8 using a 125 mmol L⁻¹ NaOH solution. In a typical experiment, 1.25 mg of CuFe₂O₄ and 1.5 mg of PMS (corresponding to 125 mg L⁻¹ of CuFe₂O₄ and 500 μmol L⁻¹ of PMS) were transferred to a 20 mL glass vial. Then, 10 mL of ultrapure H₂O (pH 8 using 22 μL of a 125 mmol L⁻¹ NaOH solution) was added to the flask to start the reaction under vigorous stirring. After 1 min reaction, 5 mL of the reaction mixture was extracted and 125 μL of a 4 mol L⁻¹ DMPO solution (final concentration of 100 mmol L⁻¹) were added to the remaining 5 mL. The resulting mixture was left under stirring for an additional 1 min. After this time, 1 mL of sample was transferred to a plastic vial that was centrifuged for 15 s at 8000 rpm. Finally, 200 μL of sample were collected and analyzed.

Fig. S2 Histogram of the as-prepared CuMF nanoparticles obtained after analyses of images (see Fig. 1 in the manuscript) obtained through transmission electron microscopy.

Table S5 Mean particle size of the as-prepared CuMF obtained from Fig. S2

Synthesis condition and thermal treatment	Mean particle size / nm
SG 400 – AsP	10 ±3
SG 400 – Us	8 ±2
SG 700 – AsP	16 ±6
Cpt 400 – AsP	4 ±1
Cpt 400 – Us	4 ±2
Cpt 700 – AsP	26 ±9

a)

b)

Fig. S3 High-resolution transmission electron micrographs for the as-prepared CuMF at distinct conditions: **a)** SG 400, **b)** SG 700, **c)** Cpt 400, and **d)** Cpt 700.

c)

d)

Fig. S3 (*continuation*) High-resolution transmission electron micrographs for the as-prepared CuMF at distinct conditions: **a)** SG 400, **b)** SG 700, **c)** Cpt 400, and **d)** Cpt 700.

Fig. S4 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the as-prepared CuMF at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h. Diffraction peaks were in accordance with the ICSD cards N° 98-001-6666 of tetragonal and N° 98-018-5895 of cubic CuFe_2O_4 .

Fig. S5 FTIR spectra the as-prepared CuMF at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S6 Deconvoluted high-resolution C 1s spectra for the as-prepared (AsP) CuMF at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S7 Deconvoluted high-resolution O 1s spectra for the as-prepared (AsP) CuMF at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S8 Deconvoluted high-resolution Cu 2p_{3/2} spectra for the as-prepared (AsP) CuMF at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Fig. S9 Deconvoluted high-resolution Fe $2p_{3/2}$ spectra for the as-prepared (AsP) CuMF at distinct experimental conditions: SG and Cpt refer to the sol-gel and co-precipitation synthesis procedure, respectively, followed by thermal treatment at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

Table S6 Pseudo first order kinetic constants (k_{1st}) obtained during *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using distinct amounts of CuMF nanoparticles.

CuMF (mg L ⁻¹)	$k_{1st} / 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R ²
62.5	1.9 ±0.3	0.96 ±0.03
125	3.6 ±0.1	0.99 ±0.01
250	7 ±1	0.995 ±0.002

Conditions: 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark. Mean values and error refer to two repetitions. The catalyst was obtained by the SG method and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h – SG 400

Table S7 Pseudo first order kinetic constants (k_{1st}) obtained during *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using CuMF nanoparticles at distinct PMS concentrations.

[PMS] ₀ (μmol L ⁻¹)	$k_{1st} / 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R ²
250	1.1 ±0.1	0.96 ±0.03
500	3.6 ±0.1	0.99 ±0.01
1000	7 ±2	0.995 ±0.002

Conditions: 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark. Mean values and error refer to two repetitions.

Table S8 Pseudo first order kinetic constants (k_{1st}) obtained during *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using CuMF nanoparticles prepared by distinct methods and thermally treated at 400 °C and 700 °C for 1 h.

PMS (μmol L ⁻¹)	$k_{1st} / 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R ²
SG 400	3.6 ±0.1	0.99 ±0.01
SG 700	6.8 ±0.8	0.997 ±0.001
Cpt 400	9.571 ± 0.004	0.9980 ±0.0005
Cpt 700	8 ±1	0.995 ±0.002

Conditions: 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark. Mean values and error refer to two repetitions.

Fig. S10 PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) using distinct **a)** loads of CuFe_2O_4 (obtained by the SG method and thermally treated at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h – SG 400) and **b)** PMS concentration values (see inset for details). **Conditions:** $500\text{ }\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L^{-1} $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, 100 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L^{-1} IMD at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S11 PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) using **a)** CuMF nanoparticles prepared and heat treated under different conditions and **b)** distinct concentration values of Cu(II) and Fe(III) ions (see inset for further details). **Conditions:** 125 mg L^{-1} CuMF, $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L^{-1} $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, 100 mL of treating solution at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Table S9 Concentration of Cu and Fe ions determined by the ICP-OES technique for the degradation experiments showed in **Table S8**.

Sample ID	[Cu] / $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	[Fe] / $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$
SG 400, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption)	30	17
SG 400, $t = 4$ h (6 h in total)	73	69
SG 700, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption)	17	15
SG 700, $t = 4$ h (6 h in total)	35	37
Cpt 400, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption)	54	53
Cpt 400, $t = 4$ h (6 h in total)	24	<QL
Cpt 700, $t = 0$ h (after 2 h adsorption)	154	248
Cpt 700, $t = 4$ h (6 h in total)	<QL	<QL

QL = Quantification limit: $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for both metals

DL = Detection limit: $4 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for both metals

Table S10 Pseudo first order kinetic constants (k_{1st}) obtained during *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using CuMF nanoparticles at distinct pH values.

pH	$k_{1st} / 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R^2
8	3.6 ± 0.1	0.99 ± 0.01
9	2.5 ± 0.3	0.985 ± 0.006
10	1.2 ± 0.1	0.96 ± 0.01

Conditions: 125 mg L^{-1} CuMF (SG 400 sample), $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, 10 mmol L^{-1} $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, 100 mL of treating solution at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All experiments were carried out in the dark. Mean values and error refer to two repetitions.

Fig. S12 PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) using **a)** distinct pH values, **b)** in the presence (w/ = with) or absence (w/o = without) of $10 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ buffer solution (see inset), and **c)** pH evolution for the condition with no pH control. **Conditions:** $125 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{ CuFe}_2\text{O}_4$ (SG 400 sample), $500 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, $10 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ (KH_2PO_4 at pH 7), 100 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L^{-1} IMD at $25 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S13 Evolution of the zeta potential (mV) as a function of solution pH for the as-prepared SG 400 sample. **Conditions:** measurements were carried out in ultrapure H₂O in the absence of buffer and IMD at 25 °C.

Table S11 Pseudo first order kinetic constants (k_{1st}) obtained during *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using CuMF nanoparticles in the presence or absence of buffer solution ($10 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$) at pH 8.

Buffer condition	$k_{1st} / 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R^2
With	3.6 ± 0.1	0.99 ± 0.01
Without	7.2 ± 0.5	0.995 ± 0.001

Conditions: 125 mg L^{-1} CuMF (SG 400 sample), $500 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, $10 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, 100 mL of treating solution at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All experiments were carried out in the dark. Mean values and error refer to two repetitions.

Fig. S14 a) Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption as a function of treatment time (t) for tap water and corresponding blank conditions (only in the presence of CuMF nanoparticles or PMS – see inset). **Conditions:** 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 μ mol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Table S12 Retention time, main detected intermediates (m/z) and error of the main detected byproducts resulting from IMD oxidation by radical species resulting from PMS activation by CuFe_2O_4 (SG 400 sample).

#	Product	t_r (min)	ESI mode		
			m/z	Attribution (ESI ⁺)	Error (ppm)
1	IMD	6.789	256.0570	[M+H] ⁺	10.1538
			209.0566	[M+H-NO ₂] ⁺	
			175.0961	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl] ⁺	
			128.0251	[M+H-HNO ₂ -C ₃ H ₆ N ₃] ⁺	
			97.0633	[M+H-NO ₂ -C ₃ H ₃ ClN] ⁺	
			84.0551	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl-C ₆ H ₅ N] ⁺	
2	P1	6.096	230.0418	[M+H] ⁺	9.1287
			186.0420	[M+H-NO ₂] ⁺	
			169.0154	[M+H-N ₂ O ₂] ⁺	
			148.0730	[M+H-NO ₂ -Cl] ⁺	
			141.0203	[M+H-CH ₂ N ₃ O ₂] ⁺	
			126.0093	[M+H-NO ₂ -CH ₃ N ₃] ⁺	
3	P2	6.145	272.0513	[M+H] ⁺	11.7623
			225.0513	[M+H-NO ₂] ⁺	
			191.0910	[M+H-NO ₂ -Cl] ⁺	
			174.0638	[M+H-N ₂ O ₂ -Cl] ⁺	
			126.0090	[M+H-NO ₂ -C ₃ H ₆ N ₃ O] ⁺	
			100.0498	[M+H-NO ₂ -Cl-C ₆ H ₅ N] ⁺	
4	P3	6.395	288.0456	[M+H] ⁺	13.1921
			241.0458	[M+H-NO ₂] ⁺	
			226.0348	[M+H-HNO ₂ -OH] ⁺	
			207.0856	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl] ⁺	
			189.0750	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			169.0148	[M+H-HNO ₂ -Cl-OH-C ₂ H ₅ N ₂] ⁺	
5	P4	7.118	157.9993	[M+H] ⁺	6.3291
			140.0349	[M+H-OH] ⁺	
			122.0227	[M+H-Cl] ⁺	
			114.0444	[M+H-COOH] ⁺	
			78.0335	[M+H-Cl-COOH] ⁺	

Conditions: 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C

Fig. S15 a) Extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) and MS/MS spectra of the main detected byproducts (4 in total) resulting from IMD oxidation by reactive oxygen species resulting from PMS activation by CuMF (SG 400 sample): **b)** IMD, **c)** P1, **d)** P2, **e)** P3 and **f)** P4. **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 25 °C and 125 mg L⁻¹ of the SG 400 sample.

Fig. S16 Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected intermediates showed in **Table S12**: **a)** IMD (m/z 256.0570), **b)** P1 (m/z 230.0418), **c)** P2 (m/z 272.0513), **d)** P3 (m/z 288.0456) and **e)** P4 (m/z 157.9993). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μ mol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 25 °C and 125 mg L⁻¹ of the SG 400 sample.

Fig. S16 (*continuation*) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected intermediates showed in **Table S12**: **a)** IMD (m/z 256.0570), **b)** P1 (m/z 230.0418), **c)** P2 (m/z 272.0513), **d)** P3 (m/z 288.0456) and **e)** P4 (m/z 157.9993). **Conditions:** 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μ mol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 25 °C and 125 mg L⁻¹ of the SG 400 sample.

Fig. S17 a) Total ion chromatogram (TIC) and **b)** Extracted ion chromatogram (EIC) of the main detected byproducts resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation by CuMF. **Conditions:** 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Table S13 Retention time and main fragment ions detected during reaction of DMPO with reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation by CuMF

#	Product	t_r (min)	ESI mode		
			m/z	Attribution (ESI ⁺)	Error (ppm)
1	DMPO/2OH	1.126	148.0962	[M+H] ⁺	8.778
			130.0076	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			115.0747	[M+H-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			97.0644	[M+H-NH ₂ OH-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			69.0696	[M+H-(OH) ₂ CNOH] ⁺	
2	DMPO	2.753	114.0916	[M+H] ⁺	2.629
			97.0811	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			81.0703	[M+H-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			72.0447	[M+H-CH(CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	
3	DMPO/OH	3.926	130.0867	[M+H] ⁺	6.918
			98.9613	[M+H-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			69.9941	[M+H-CH ₃ NO ₂] ⁺	
			61.0079	[M+H-C ₅ H ₉] ⁺	
			55.0543	[M+H-C ₂ H ₅ NO ₂] ⁺	
4	2DMPO/O-3H	4.820	241.1564	[M+H] ⁺	7.049
			224.1564	[M+H-OH] ⁺	
			209.1295	[M+H-OH-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			191.1194	[M+H-OH-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			128.1078	[M+H-C ₆ H ₁₁ NO] ⁺	
			114.0921	[M+H-C ₆ H ₁₂ NO ₂] ⁺	
			94.0656	[M+H-C ₆ H ₁₀ NO ₂ -OH] ⁺	
5	2DMPO/-H	4.415	227.1774	[M+H] ⁺	8.803
			209.1664	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			194.1554	[M+H-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			177.1407	[M+H-NH ₂ OH-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			114.0923	[M+H-H ₂ O-C ₆ H ₁₀ N] ⁺	
			96.0817	[M+H-C ₆ H ₁₃ NO ₂] ⁺	
			81.0050	[M+H-H ₂ O-C ₆ H ₁₀ NO] ⁺	
			74.0608	[M+H-H ₂ O-CH ₂ (CH ₃) ₂] ⁺	
6	2DMPO/-3H	5.142	225.1615	[M+H] ⁺	7.106
			207.1508	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
			189.1398	[M+H-2H ₂ O] ⁺	
			175.1244	[M+H-H ₂ O-NH ₂ OH] ⁺	
			112.0764	[M+H-C ₆ H ₁₁ NO] ⁺	
			94.0657	[M+H-H ₂ O-NH ₂ OH-C ₆ H ₉] ⁺	
			69.0705	[M+H-C ₆ H ₈ N-C ₂ H ₅ NO] ⁺	

Conditions: 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S18 MS/MS spectra of the main detected byproducts resulting from the reaction resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation by CuMF: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H. **Conditions:** 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S19 Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected DMPO intermediates resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation by CuMF: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H **Conditions:** 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S19 (*continuation*) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected DMPO intermediates resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation by CuMF: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H Conditions: 125 mg L^{-1} CuMF (SG 400 sample), $500 \text{ } \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, 10 mmol L^{-1} $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$, 100 mL of treating solution at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S19 (continuation) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected DMPO intermediates resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation by CuMF: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H Conditions: 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S19 (*continuation*) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected DMPO intermediates resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation by CuMF: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H Conditions: 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S19 (continuation) Proposed fragmentation route of the main detected DMPO intermediates resulting from reaction between DMPO and reactive oxygen species produced during PMS activation by CuMF: **a)** DMPO/2OH, **b)** DMPO, **c)** DMPO/OH, **d)** 2DMPO/O-3H, **e)** 2DMPO/-H, and **f)** 2DMPO/-3H Conditions: 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400 sample), 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S20 - Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) as a function of treatment time (t) using distinct compounds (isopropyl alcohol (IPA), furfuryl alcohol (FFA), t-butyl alcohol (TBA), and L-histidine (L-H)) as scavengers. **Conditions:** 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF (SG 400), 500 μ mol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

Fig. S21 - Evolution of dissolved oxygen as a function of time (t) at distinct experimental conditions (see inset). **Conditions:** No IMD addition, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇ at 25 °C and using the SG 400 sample.

Fig. S22 Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) as a function of treatment time (t) using CuMF prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally treated at 400 °C during 1 h (SG 400) for the recycling test. **Conditions:** 125 mg L⁻¹ CuMF, 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD, 500 μmol L⁻¹ PMS, pH 8.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ Na₂B₄O₇, 100 mL of treating solution at 25 °C. All experiments were carried out in the dark.

a)

b)

Fig. S23 Histogram of the as-prepared (AsP) and used (Us) CuMF nanoparticles synthesized by the **a)** sol-gel and **b)** co-precipitation methods and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1h. Data were obtained from transmission electron microscopy images.

Fig. S24 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CuMF synthesized by the sol-gel (SG) method and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h, *i.e.*, SG 400 and SG 700 (see inset), respectively. Diffraction peaks were in accordance with the ICSD cards N° 98-001-6666 (tetragonal) and N° 98-018-5895 (cubic).

Fig. S25 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CuMF synthesized by the co-precipitation (Cpt) method and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h, *i.e.*, Cpt 400 and Cpt 700 (see inset), respectively. Diffraction peaks were in accordance with the ICSD cards N° 98-001-6666 (tetragonal) and N° 98-018-5895 (cubic).

Fig. S26 FTIR spectra of the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CuMF synthesized by the sol-gel (SG) method and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h, *i.e.*, SG 400 and SG 700 (see inset), respectively.

Fig. S27 FTIR spectra of the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CuMF synthesized by the co-precipitation (Cpt) method and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h, *i.e.*, Cpt 400 and Cpt 700 (see inset), respectively.

a)

b)

Fig. S28 Deconvoluted high-resolution C 1s spectra for the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CuMF synthesized by the **a)** sol-gel (SG) and **b)** co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

a)

b)

Fig. S29 Deconvoluted high-resolution O 1s spectra for the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CuMF synthesized by the **a)** sol-gel (SG) and **b)** co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C.

a)

b)

Fig. S30 Deconvoluted high-resolution Fe 2p_{3/2} spectra for the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CuMF synthesized by the **a)** sol-gel (SG) and **b)** co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C.

a)

b)

Fig. S31 Deconvoluted high-resolution Cu 2p_{3/2} spectra for the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) CuMF synthesized by the **a)** sol-gel (SG) and **b)** co-precipitation (Cpt) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C.

Fig. S32 Peak areas of the surface bonding chemical states obtained from the O 1s spectra (see **Fig. S29**) using the **a)** sol-gel (SG) and **b)** co-precipitation (Cpt) samples that were thermally treated at 400 °C or 700 °C for 1 h.

a)

b)

Fig. S33 a) Complex plane and **b)** Bode plots for the CuMF samples (in the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) – see legend in the inset) obtained by the sol-gel method and heat treated at 400 °C for 1 h (SG 400). The equivalent circuit used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance are in the inset of **a)**. A 0.5 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ (no pH correction) solution at ambient conditions was used.

a)

b)

Fig. S34 a) Complex plane and **b)** Bode plots for the CuMF samples (in the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) – see legend in the inset) obtained by the sol-gel method and heat treated at 700 °C for 1 h (SG 700). The equivalent circuit used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance are in the inset of **a)**. A 0.5 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ (no pH correction) solution at ambient conditions was used.

a)

b)

Fig. S35 Complex plane and **b)** Bode plots for the CuMF samples (in the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) – see legend in the inset) obtained by the co-precipitation method and heat treated at 400 °C for 1 h (Cpt 400). The equivalent circuit used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance are in the inset of **a)**. A 0.5 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ (no pH correction) solution at ambient conditions was used.

a)

b)

Fig. S36 a) Complex plane, b) Bode plots for the CuMF samples (in the as-prepared (AsP) and after use (Us) – see legend in the inset) obtained by the co-precipitation method and heat treated at 700 °C for 1 h (Cpt 700), and c) the equivalent circuit used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance. A 0.5 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ (no pH correction) solution at ambient conditions was used.